

ON FUZZY DECISION MAKING MODELING IN DIAGNOSING EYE DISEASES BASED ON FEEDBACK EXTENSION

A. Venkatesh* & G. Sivakumar**

Department of Mathematics, A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College (Autonomous), Poondi, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: A. Venkatesh & G. Sivakumar, “On Fuzzy Decision Making Modeling in Diagnosing Eye Diseases Based on Feedback Extension”, International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page

Number 138-140, 2017.

Abstract:

Diagnosis of eye disorders is initially based on the person's symptoms, the appearance of the eyes, and the results of an examination. Sometimes eye symptoms develop as part of an illness that affects several organ systems. In this paper, fuzzy decision making techniques based on feedback extension is used, to evolve a diagnostic technique for diagnosing patient with complaints in eye sight.

Key Words: Multi Objective Linear Model, Fuzzy Linear Programming Problem, Fuzzy Number & Communicable Diseases

1. Introduction:

For many of the common diseases, medical diagnosis involves procedures that are only approximate to arrive at the correct diagnosis [2]. The medical diagnosis procedure for the determination of various types of diseases is generally observed by using the inherent property of fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic [5]. The essence of fuzzy logic is to provide a linguistic approach with better approximation [3].

Most of the problems of real life have various uncertainties. Traditional mathematical tools are unable to solve uncertain problems. There are theories viz. theories of probability, theory of evidence, stochastic process, image processing for dealing with uncertainties [6, 7].

These theories have their own difficulties. The reason for these difficulties is inadequacy of parameterization tool of the theories. Zadeh [1] proposed novel concept of fuzzy set theory in his pioneering paper.

In this paper, we suggested a procedure for the diagnosis of Eye diseases which is based on feedback extension of fuzzy decision making technique.

2. Basic Definitions:

2.1 Atomic Factor:

A factor f is called an atomic factor if f does not have proper subfactors except for the zero factor.

Let F be the class of factors the set of all atomic factors in F is called the family of atomic factors which is denoted by π

2.2 Representation Extension:

For a given description frame (U, C, F) , let $\alpha \in C$, whose extension is $\tilde{A} \in f(u)$ for any $f \in F$, define $f(\tilde{A}) : x(f) \rightarrow [0,1], x \rightarrow f(\tilde{A})(x) = \bigvee_{f(u)=x} \tilde{A}(u)$

Then $f(\tilde{A})$ is a fuzzy subset of the representation universe $x(f)$. $f(\tilde{A}) \in f(x(f))$, and $f(\tilde{A})$ is called the representation extension of α in the representation universe $x(f)$.

2.3 Feedback Extension:

Let (U, C, F) be a description frame, $\alpha \in C$ and $f \in F$. Assume $\tilde{B}(f)$ to be the known representation extension of the concept α is the representation universe $X(f)$. Define

$$f^{-1}(\tilde{B}(f)) : U \rightarrow [0,1]$$

$$u \rightarrow f^{-1}(\tilde{B}(f))(u) = \tilde{B}(f)(f(u))$$

Then $f^{-1}(\tilde{B}(f))$ is a fuzzy subset of the universe U . it is called feedback extension with respect to f .

3. An Implementation Procedure for Orderable Decision Making Based on Feedback Extension is Discussed:

Define a tactics set $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ which is a group of tactics or strategies.

Determine the concept α in $C = \{\alpha\}$ and name that concept. U is the universe of the concept α .

Determine the set of atomic factors $\pi = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$ on U and its factor spaces $\{X(f_j)\}_{(1 \leq j \leq m)}$

Let $F = P(\pi)$. Then (U, C, F) is a description frame.

Construct $\tilde{B}(f), 1 \leq i \leq m$, the representation of α , on the representation universes $X(f_j), 1 \leq j \leq m$.

Take an appropriate m – dimensional triangular norm T_m and form the representation extension $\tilde{B}(1)$ in $X(1)$ from T_m and $\tilde{B}(f_i)$ as in

$$\tilde{B}(1)(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) = T_m(\tilde{B}(f_1)(x_1), \tilde{B}(f_2)(x_2), \dots, \tilde{B}(f_m)(x_m))$$

Determine $f_j(u_j)$, the state of the tactic i on the atomic factor j , where $i=1,2,\dots,n$ and $j = 1,2,\dots,m$.

Then we obtain the state of the complete factor 1 on each tactic as in

$$1(u_i) = (f_1(u_i), f_2(u_i), \dots, f_m(u_i)) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Construct $1^{-1}(\tilde{B}(1))$, the feedback extension of α , which is regarded as the approximation of \tilde{A} . For any $u_i \in U$, then

$$\begin{aligned} A(u_i) &\approx (1^{-1}(\tilde{B}(1)))(u_i) = \tilde{B}(1)(1(u_i)) \\ &= \tilde{B}(1)(f_1(u_i), f_2(u_i), \dots, f_m(u_i)) \\ &= T_m(\tilde{B}(f_1)(f_1(u_i)), \tilde{B}(f_2)(f_2(u_i)), \dots, \tilde{B}(f_m)(f_m(u_i))) \end{aligned}$$

Now we can proceed to pick the best tactic u_i^* by the principles of maximum membership.

4. A Diagnostic Technique for the Diagnosis of the Patients with Eye Compliant is Evolved Using Orderable Decision Making Based on Feedback Extension:

Let us consider the problem of how to diagnose the patients with an eye compliant among the three diseases.

Let d_1 = Cataract, d_2 = Glaucomad, d_3 = Uveitis

Define α = “Most Probable Disease”, then $C = \{ \alpha \} = \{ \text{Most probable disease} \}$

Let f_1 = Diminished vision

f_2 = Eye pain

f_3 = Dart spots

f_4 = Redness of the eye

Consider the set $\pi = \{ f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4 \}$

and $X(f_j) = [0, 100], j = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Let $F = P(\pi)$, then (U, C, F) is a description frame.

$$\text{Define } \tilde{B}(f_j)(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & 90 \leq x \leq 100 \\ \frac{x-60}{30} & 60 \leq x \leq 90 \\ 0 & 0 \leq x \leq 60 \end{cases}$$

Construct $T_m \in T(4)$, a four dimensional triangular norms as

$$T4 = T_4 = x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot x_3 \cdot x_4 = \prod_{j=1}^4 x_j$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}(1)(x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot x_3 \cdot x_4) &= T4(\tilde{B}(f_1)(x_1), \tilde{B}(f_2)(x_2), \tilde{B}(f_3)(x_3), \tilde{B}(f_4)(x_4)) \\ &= \tilde{B}(f_1)(x_1) \cdot \tilde{B}(f_2)(x_2) \cdot \tilde{B}(f_3)(x_3) \cdot \tilde{B}(f_4)(x_4) \end{aligned}$$

The percentage of the factors (f_j) and each disease (d_i) given in the following

d / f	Diminished vision (f_1)	Eye pain (f_2)	Dart spots (f_3)	Redness of the eye (f_4)
Cataract (d_1)	75	95	93	92
Glaucomad (d_2)	85	75	85	83
Uveitis (d_3)	95	85	70	80

The corresponding membership function values $\tilde{B}(f_i)(f(d_i))$ are given as follows:

d / f	Diminished vision (f_1)	Eye pain (f_2)	Dart spots (f_3)	Redness of the eye (f_4)
Cataract (d_1)	0.5	1	1	1
Glaucomad (d_2)	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.7
Uveitis (d_3)	1	0.8	0.3	0.6

Calculate $\tilde{A}(d_i)$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{A}(d_1) &= \tilde{B}(1)(f_j(d_1)) \\ &= \tilde{B}(1)((f_1(d_1)) \cdot (f_2(d_1)) \cdot (f_3(d_1)) \cdot (f_4(d_1))) \\ &= T(\tilde{B}(f_1)(f_1(d_1)) \cdot \tilde{B}(f_2)(f_2(d_1)) \cdot \tilde{B}(f_3)(f_3(d_1)) \cdot \tilde{B}(f_4)(f_4(d_1))) \\ &= 0.5 \times 1 \times 1 \times 1 \\ \tilde{A}(d_1) &= 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly we get,

$$\tilde{A}(d_2) = 0.2$$

$$\tilde{A}(d_3) = 0.1$$

So Cataract is a probable disease of the three.

Conclusion:

Thus fuzzy set theory has made applications in the field of decision science [4]. The concept of factor spaces is the foundation for fuzzy decision making through this frame work an interesting method of fuzzy decision making is developed and using this method a diagnostic technique is evolved.

References:

1. Bellman, R. E., Zadeh, L. A., Decision making in a fuzzy environment, Management Sci., 17 (1970), 141-164.
2. David Sons, Principles and practice of medicine, 7th Edition.
3. Klir, G. J., Yuan, B., Fuzzy Sets and Fuzzy Logic: Theory and Applications, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1995.
4. Li – Hong – Xing & Vincent. C. Yen: Fuzzy sets and fuzzy decision making, 1953.
5. Li – Hong – Xing: Fuzzy Mathematics Methods in Engineering and its Applications, Tianjin Scientific and Technical Press, Tianjin, 1993.
6. Mason J.E., et al., (2012), Optimizing Statin Treatment Decisions for Diabetes Patients in the Presence of Uncertain Future Adherence. Med Decis Making, 32(1), pp.154 – 156.
7. Persi Pamela, I. et al., (2013), A Fuzzy Optimization Technique for the Prediction of Coronary Heart Disease Using Decision Tree, International Journal of Engineering and Technology, 5(3), pp. 2506 – 2514.